

A Straightforward Chemical Synthesis for 2-ethyl-2-methylpentane-1,4-diamine

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For this procedure you will need the following base materials:

2-bromo-2-methylpentane	100mL
Sodium Cyanide (NaCN)	0.91g
Solvent (e.g., DMSO)	1.09mL

In a well-ventilated hood, set up a reaction vessel with a condenser and a magnetic stirrer. Add 1.09mL of a suitable solvent (e.g., DMSO, if DMSO is not available I suggest using Toluene or Acetonitrile, though it has a lower boiling point than DMSO) to the reaction vessel, then add 100mL C₆H₁₃Br and 0.91g NaCN. Heat the reaction mixture slowly while stirring. Maintain the temperature at around 80-90°C for several hours (around 4-6 hours), this will allow for the nucleophilic substitution reaction to occur. After the reaction is complete, cool the mixture to room temperature.

Carefully quench the reaction by adding water or an acid solution (e.g., hydrochloric acid) to hydrolyze any possible unreacted cyanide. Extract the organic layer containing the product with an appropriate ORGANIC solvent (e.g., diethyl ether). Wash the organic layer with water and then dry it over anhydrous sodium sulfate to improve the yield. You can do this by mixing the organic layer with water in a separating funnel or similar container. Evaporate the solvent, and you're left with 1,3-adamantanediamine. You should have approximately 2.5g of the 1,3-adamantanediamine (C₁₀H₁₈N₂)

For the reduction of 2-ethyl-2-methylpentane-1,4-dinitrile the following base ingredients are needed:

1,3-adamantanediamine	2.5g
Lithium aluminum hydride (LiAlH ₄)	0.4g
Dry ether (e.g., diethyl ether)	Dependent on yield.

In a dry and inert atmosphere, set up a reaction vessel with a condenser and a magnetic stirrer. NO₂ preferred over Argon but Argon can still be used. Add dry ether to the reaction vessel and then add LiAlH₄ dropwise or gradual but be cautious as lithium aluminum hydride reactions are usually exothermic. Slowly add the 1,3-adamantanediamine to the mixture, I advise you to set up an ice bath at around -0.5°C. Allow the reaction to proceed for several hours (typically 4-6 hours) at this low temperature. This is for a variety of reasons but it's mostly to safely control and stabilize the reaction rate of LiAlH₄, as well as quench any excess of it. Now, carefully quench the reaction by adding water slowly, preferably dropwise to the mixture.

After the reaction is complete, extract the amine using an ORGANIC solvent (e.g., diethyl ether). Transfer the reaction mixture into a separatory funnel and add an appropriate aqueous solution (acid or base) to create two layers (HCl or NaOH). Gently mix and vent the funnel, allowing the layers to separate. Drain the upper organic layer (containing the amine) into a container. Dry and concentrate the final product using diethyl ether under reduced pressure environment. The final product should be 2-ethyl-2-methylpentane-1,4-diamine.

Warning:

2-ethyl-2-methylpentane-1,4-diamine is a potentially hazardous chemical. Handle it with care, wearing appropriate safety gear and following established safety protocols, including proper storage in a well-ventilated and labeled container.